

An approximate quantity of 1 M NaClO₄ solution was added to each of the above mixtures to maintain constant ionic strength of 0.1 M. The total volume of each of the mixtures was made up to 50 ml so that the solutions were 50% (v/v) with respect to dioxane. A Elico LI-120 pH meter (accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit) with glass and calomel electrodes, was used to record the pH values. All the measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. These practical values were converted into thermodynamic values by applying Van Uitert and Fernelius correction⁹. The deprotonation constants of the ligands along with the stability constants of the metal–ligand complexes evaluated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹⁰ are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TRANSITION METAL- β -DIKETONE COMPLEXES IN 50% (v/v) AQUEOUS DIOXANE

Metal ion	F-3',4'-DMPPD		F-3',5'-DMPPD		F-3',6'-DMPPD	
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
H ⁺	8.88	—	9.34	—	8.77	—
Ni ²⁺	6.51	5.13	6.22	4.68	5.52	3.65
Co ²⁺	6.07	5.24	5.98	4.65	5.23	3.54
Zn ²⁺	5.76	4.80	5.68	4.60	5.02	3.43
Mn ²⁺	4.90	4.43	4.85	4.50	4.70	3.35

Standard deviation: ± 0.02 .

Results and Discussion

The pK values of acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane and 2-furoylbenzoylmethane are 12.70, 12.85, 13.75 and 12.95, respectively, in dioxane–water (3:1) medium⁹. In these compounds, however, there is no phenolic OH groups and hence pK values refer to the deprotonation of the compounds in their enol form due to keto-enol tautomerism. The deprotonation for present β -diketones refers to the phenolic OH group and comparable to pK value (10.50) of phenol¹¹ in 1:1 (v/v) dioxane–water medium. Thus, there is lowering of pK values (*i.e.* increase in acid strength) for the present ligands. The second deprotonation arising out of keto-enol tautomerism of these ligands could not be followed in the present study.

The difference between log K₁ and log K₂ of metal–ligand complexes were less than 1.78 log units, suggesting overlapping of the successive formation of both the complexes. The formation for the metal complexes with F-3',5'-DMPPD, and F-3',6'-DMPPD were however incomplete due to precipitation. The log K₂ values in these cases were therefore calculated by the mid-point method¹⁰ using equation, $\log K_1 K_2 = 2 pL$ (at $\bar{n} = 1.0$). With respect to ligands, the stability sequence was F-3',6'-DMPPD < F-3',4'-DMPPD < F-3',5'-DMPPD, and this should be in accordance with their basicities. The stability of the

different complexes investigated follow the order, Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Mn²⁺ which is in accordance with Mellor and Malley¹². There was a linear relationship between log K and pK values suggesting identical binding sites in all the ligands.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the authorities of the Marathwada University, Aurangabad, for facilities. One of the authors (D.S.D) gratefully acknowledges the cooperation by S. B. Science College, Aurangabad.

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Dithiocarbamate Anions as Salts of Oxinatobis-(η^5 -indenyl)titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) Chelates

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Manuscript received 1 June 1983, revised 19 November 1986, accepted 3 January 1987

DURING the course of our recent investigations¹⁻³ we have elucidated that the coordination of two nitrogen and two oxygen atoms to (η^5 -R) (η^5 -R')M(IV) moiety would lead to the weakening of the metal ring bonds (R=C₄H₄N, R'=C₅H₅, C₅H₇; R=C₅H₅, R'=C₅H₇; M=Ti,

Zr). In order to investigate whether or not the coordination of two nitrogen and two oxygen atoms around $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{M(IV)}$ moiety would produce a similar weakening of metal ring bonds, we studied the interaction of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{MCl}_2$ ($\text{M}=\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}$ or Zr^{IV}) with 8-hydroxyquinoline (oxine) in aqueous medium. We failed to isolate a derivative in which two oxinato groups coordinate to the $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{M(IV)}$ moiety. However, ionic complexes of the type, $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ML}]^+\text{Cl}^-$ (L is the conjugate base of oxine) in which oxinate ligand is coordinated to the M(IV) ion in a bidentate fashion were readily obtained.

Experimental

Nitrobenzene for conductance measurements was purified by the method described by Fay and Lowry⁴. Bis(η^5 -indenyl) M(IV) dichlorides were prepared by the reaction of MCl_4 with sodium indaide in THF⁵. Sodium dithiocarbamates were prepared by the method of Gilman and Blatt⁵.

An aqueous solution of $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ML}]^+\text{Cl}^-$ ($\text{M}=\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}$ or Zr^{IV} ; L=conjugate base of oxine) was obtained by stirring a 50 ml aqueous solution of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ (3.5 g, 0.001 mol) or $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ (3.9 g, 0.001 mol) with oxine (1.45 g, 0.001 mol) for ~1 h. The solution was filtered and portions of the filtrate added separately to aqueous solutions of sodium dithiocarbamates. The resulting green precipitates were filtered and washed with petroleum ether. The complexes were reprecipitated from acetone solution by the addition of petroleum ether.

Conductance measurements were made on a digital direct reading conductivity meter 304. Solid state ir spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} using a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded at a sweep width of 900 Hz with a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer. Chemical shifts are expressed relative to internal TMS (1% by volume).

Results and Discussion

The dithiocarbamate derivatives, $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ML}]^+\text{X}^-$ were green in colour and thermally quite stable, and soluble in acetone, THF and DMSO. Conductivity measurements in nitrobenzene show all the complexes to be 1:1 electrolytes. The analytical data and physical characteristics of the complexes are listed in Table 1.

The infrared spectra of the $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ML}]^+\text{X}^-$ complexes showed a strong band at ~1450 cm^{-1} due to C=N bond in the dithiocarbamate anion⁷. Strong band due to $\nu_{\text{O-N}}$ stretching of the oxinate group was observed at a lower frequency (~1330 cm^{-1}) than that in free oxine (~1500 cm^{-1}). This indicated considerably less double bond character of the C-N bond in the oxinato group in the complexes. It may be assumed that the lone pair on nitrogen is involved in the formation of a coordinate bond with the M(IV) ion, thus reducing double bond formation of the C=N bond as compared to the free oxine. Further, the $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ stretching which appeared at ~3200 cm^{-1} in free oxine, disappeared on complexation, thus indicating that the oxinato group is chelating. The ~1000 cm^{-1} band was attributed to the C=S stretching in the dithiocarbamate anion. A doublet was observed at $500 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the peak at higher frequency being assigned to C-O in-plane bending⁸ and that at lower frequency to M-O stretching vibrations⁹.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ML}]^+\text{X}^-$ complexes show no trace of the free ligand indicating that the complexes dissociate very little upon dissolution in DMSO. The resonance due to the proton at C₂ (δ 9.05, q, J 4.0Hz, 1.8Hz) of the oxinate group was observed at a lower field compared to that of the free oxine (δ 8.73). This supported the conclusion that the oxinate ligand is chelating⁹.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Decomp. temp. °C	Λ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		
			Ti/Zn	N	S
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{TiL}]^+[\text{Me}_2\text{NCS}_2]^-$	83	26.8	8.96 (8.85)	5.31 (5.40)	12.23 (12.36)
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{TiL}]^+[\text{Et}_2\text{NCS}_2]^-$	72	24.8	8.55 (8.42)	5.00 (5.12)	11.83 (11.72)
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{TiL}]^+[\text{i-Pr}_2\text{NCS}_2]^-$	82	28.2	8.13 (8.02)	4.76 (4.87)	11.02 (11.15)
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ZrL}]^+[\text{Me}_2\text{NCS}_2]^-$	165	29.4	15.68 (15.58)	4.86 (4.98)	11.27 (11.40)
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ZrL}]^+[\text{Et}_2\text{NCS}_2]^-$	165	27.8	14.75 (14.87)	4.64 (4.75)	10.98 (10.86)
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{ZrL}]^+[\text{i-PrNCS}_2]^-$	160	26.6	14.35 (14.22)	4.41 (4.53)	10.21 (10.36)

*HL = oxine.

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Coordination Template Reactions Part II. Complexes of Macrocyclic Ligand (TAAB) Tetrabenzob[*b,f,j,u*]-1,5,9,13-tetrazacyclohexadecine with Dioxouranium(II), Oxovanadium(II), Oxotitanium(II) and Oxozirconium(II) Ions

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*Manuscript received 13 November 1985, revised 19 May 1986,
accepted 26 November 1986*

IN a previous communication from this laboratory some complexes of the title ligand with Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} were reported¹. In continuation of our work on macrocyclic complexes, the synthesis and characterisation of complexes of UO_2^{2+} , VO^{2+} , TiO^{2+} and ZrO^{2+} ions with the above mentioned ligand are characterised and reported in the present communication.

Keeping in view the fact that the formation of macrocycle depends upon the nature of metal, anion as well as the resulting closed ring geometry, it is found that in the present complexes, only four molecules of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde condense together to give the tetradentate ligand, while the oxygen atoms occupy the other vacant positions of the co-ordination geometry. The anions, though otherwise coordinating in nature, are outside the coordination sphere in all the complexes, as expected.

The complexes were prepared by adding the corresponding oxo-metal acetates, sulphates or

chlorides to a refluxing solution of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde freshly prepared by standard method. The resulting solution assumed a viscous appearance after refluxing for 10 h and the complexes were separated from the solution by treatment with petroleum ether—ethanol mixture. For the preparation of thiocyanate or oxalate complexes, the same procedures as described above was used, but to the refluxing solution containing oxometal chloride calculated amount of ammonium thiocyanate or oxalate was added and the ammonium chloride so formed was removed by filtration.

The elemental analysis data show that in case of all the oxo cations, only one molecule of ligand (obtained by intramolecular condensation of four molecules of aldehyde) is coordinated. The molar conductances in nitrobenzene are in the usual range of electrolytes and thus the anions are not coordinated in any case as indicated in the formulae of the complexes given in Table I. As evident, this type of condensation results in the formation of the macrocyclic ligand TAAB which completely encircles the metal ion through its four azomethine nitrogen atoms. The metal ions on the other hand acts as template directing the steric course of the reaction in the above manner and a planar completely closed ring structures results around the metal ions. The two oxygen atoms of UO_2^{2+} and one of VO^{2+} , TiO^{2+} and ZrO^{2+} are placed at the axial positions of the octahedron or square-pyramid and thus project outside the planar macrocyclic ring.

In the infrared spectra of the complexes, the NH_2 and CO stretching frequencies are absent, and a sharp band appears at 1620 cm^{-1} due to azomethine stretch and confirms the fact that Schiff base condensation with the consequent formation of macrocycle has occurred. The negative shift in its frequency of 40 cm^{-1} or more is due to its coordination^{2,3}. The infrared spectra of all the anions exhibit characteristic non-coordinated frequencies⁴⁻⁶. The $\text{U}=\text{O}$, $\text{V}=\text{O}$, $\text{Ti}=\text{O}$ and $\text{Zr}=\text{O}$ stretching frequencies are observed around 910 ± 5 , 950 ± 10 , 1050 ± 10 and $970 \pm 5\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, as reported for other similar complexes, and establish the presence of oxo-ions in these complexes⁷⁻¹¹.

Except the VO^{2+} ion, all the other oxo-ions are d^0 systems and thus their complexes are diamagnetic in nature. In their electronic spectra only charge transfer bands are seen. The magnetic moment of VO^{2+} complexes are 1.90–1.60 B.M., which is the usual range of one unpaired electron. In the electronic spectra, three bands are expected in the range 12.00–15.00, 14.50–19.00 and 21.00–30.00 kK and though their meaningful assignment has been found to be slightly difficult, the last band which is observed in the present complexes at 22.00 kK may be due to the charge transfer transition between the d_{z^2} orbital of vanadium and 2px or 2py